

Smart Manufacturing System Using LLM for Human-Robot Collaboration: Applications and Challenges

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Abstract:

In the era of Industry 4.0, emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and the internet of things (IoT) are rapidly transforming and upgrading the manufacturing industry, with robots playing an increasingly crucial role in this process. These advancements lay the foundation for high-quality development in intelligent manufacturing. With the introduction of Industry 5.0, the human-centered approach has gained significant attention, giving rise to a new field of human-centric manufacturing. The distinction between humans and robots in intelligent manufacturing systems is becoming increasingly blurred, and research on human-robot collaboration has become a hot topic. This paper proposes a

prototype method for human-robot smart collaborative operation in intelligent manufacturing systems, based on the integration of large language model (LLM) and machine vision. By leveraging the strengths of computer vision and LLMs, the method aims to enhance the intelligence of human-robot smart collaboration in manufacturing systems. Additionally, this study discussed the applications and challenges of this proposed model.

Keywords: Industry 5.0, human-robot collaboration, smart manufacturing systems, large language model, machine vision.

Introduction

The introduction of Industry 4.0 has propelled the industrial sector into a fast-paced

transformation, driven by the accelerating development of technologies such as AI, big data, digital twin, and the IoT, resulting in

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significant advancements (Shoukat, et al., 2022a; Niaz, et al., 2022; Shoukat, et al., 2024b). Recently, Industry 5.0, driven by value, has garnered increasing attention, with the “human-centered” concept gaining widespread recognition, giving rise to a new field of “human-centric intelligent manufacturing” (Rani, et al., 2024). Human-robot collaboration (HRC) has emerged as a typical application of the human-centered philosophy in intelligent manufacturing systems (Shoukat, et al., 2022b).

The HRC operation in intelligent manufacturing systems generally refers to the process where operators and robots work together in the same manufacturing environment to complete tasks (Shoukat, et al., 2024a). On one hand, the operator is the “soul” of HRC, bringing flexibility and creativity; on the other hand, robots typically take on roles involving simple, repetitive, and physically demanding tasks. In fact, the interaction and collaboration between humans and machines or robots has been an issue since the advent of machines. Initially, due to historical technological limitations, HRC had to occur in environments that were absolutely safe, often through the use of physical barriers and time-staggered collaboration, which did not fully leverage the strengths of both humans and robots. As technology has developed and new forms of production relationships have emerged, synchronous collaboration between humans and robots in the same work environment has become increasingly possible. HRC is becoming more intelligent and natural, with more efficient and seamless collaboration between humans and robots.

In light of these goals, researchers have conducted a series of studies on topics such as HRC state sensing and robot task path planning, accumulating a wealth of theoretical and methodological results. For instance, Wang et al. (2018) proposed a deep learning-based human action recognition method for predicting collaborative work situations, introducing two AlexNet models for recognizing human motion and tool recognition. Al-Amin et al. (2023) developed a deep learning classifier based on skeletal data for personalized assembly motion recognition, improving the accuracy of worker

motion recognition. Bilberg et al. (2019) projected an object-oriented event-driven simulation method to achieve real-time human-robot collaborative control and dynamic task allocation based on skills, exploring highly flexible human-robot collaboration models under the influence of digital twin technologies. Zhu et al. (2022) investigated the layout reconstruction of intelligent manufacturing cells in HRC systems, establishing a multi-objective optimization model based on time, cost, and human-robot idle time, and solving it using the NSGA-II algorithm to dynamically optimize the human-robot collaboration layout and improve production efficiency.

Liu et al. (2018) reviewed gesture recognition technologies and algorithms, discussing their application in human-robot collaborative operations, and established a comprehensive human-robot collaboration gesture recognition model covering sensing, recognition, tracking, and classification. Duan et al. (2024) proposed a dual-robot assembly system framework for human-robot collaboration based on multimodal sensing, providing multimodal information interaction through gesture, voice, human body, and visual perception for robot control. Ye et al. (2023) introduced ChatGPT to enhance the mutual trust between humans and robots in the collaborative process, ensuring task safety.

From the existing research, it is clear that HRC is a dynamic and rapidly evolving field. Researchers are constantly integrating new technologies such as digital twins, deep learning, and LLM to improve collaborative efficiency and mutual trust (Shoukat, et al., 2024c; Shah, et al., 2024; Mi, et al., 2024). However, existing studies tend to focus on specific aspects of the HRC process, such as gesture recognition or mutual trust, with limited research on how robots can better understand production tasks and operator intent to autonomously collaborate. With the accelerated application of machine vision and the rapid development of AI technologies, especially the emergence and vertical applications of LLMs, new technological foundations and possibilities have been provided

for achieving human-robot smart collaboration in manufacturing.

In this context, this paper proposes a method for human-robot smart collaborative operation in intelligent manufacturing systems, driven by visual perception and supported by LLMs for decision-making. The method aims to establish a cognitive chain between operators and robots in the collaboration process, achieving autonomous collaboration between humans and robots and providing a crucial lever for realizing human-robot integration.

- First, the paper provides a detailed analysis of the HRC operation process and its challenges in intelligent manufacturing systems.
- Then, it establishes a machine vision system using deep cameras, integrating YOLOv7 and transfer learning to identify the state of task objects, while leveraging long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and attention mechanisms to dynamically track the operator's actions.

- Further, the LLM is fine-tuned to meet the needs of HRC and a decision-making framework based on the fine-tuned model is established to facilitate dynamic collaboration between the operator and robot.

Research Framework for HRC Operation

Currently, in the execution process of human-machine collaborative operations within intelligent manufacturing systems, the relationship between operators and robots is shifting from the traditional "master-slave" model to a "partner" model. This has given rise to a new type of robot—Collaborative Robots (Cobots) (Liu, et al., 2024; Bisen, & Payal, 2022). Compared to traditional industrial robots, cobots emphasize the complementary advantages of operators and robots during production tasks, with the premise of ensuring the safety of the operators, to jointly accomplish the production goals (Javaid, et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Framework for Human-Robot Smart Collaborative Operations

In a typical collaborative operation process, two or more operators reach a consensus on the tasks to be performed and dynamically recognize the operational status of their partners during the

execution. This allows for adjustments to the tasks in real time to ensure that the work is completed more effectively. In human-machine collaborative operations, collaboration among

human operators serves as an important benchmark for evolution (Shoukat, et al., 2022; Habib, et al., 2021). This collaboration is also a key focus in the research and application of human-machine collaborative work theories and methods. Specifically, in human-machine collaboration, how to better understand the operator's intentions, make quick and accurate collaborative decisions, and efficiently and safely complete the tasks is an urgent issue that needs to be addressed and is currently a hot research topic. Therefore, this paper will focus on the identification of operator intentions and robot decision-making processes within the human-machine collaborative operation of intelligent manufacturing systems. The goal is to achieve autonomous and collaborative operation between humans and machines, as shown in Figure 1.

Production tasks are dynamically assigned, involving product types, process planning, operating procedures, and other necessary information, while considering the characteristics of both the robots and operators to allocate tasks (predefined). Based on this, with support from machine vision, deep learning, and large models, robots will establish intelligent perception and decision-making paths. This allows them to form a collaborative operational cognition link with human operators and efficiently and accurately complete the production tasks through autonomous and dynamic interaction.

Fusion of Machine Vision and Deep Learning for HRC

In intelligent manufacturing systems, accurate perception of the work state is crucial for human-machine smart collaboration. By sensing the current work state, collaborative robots can real-time recognize the operator's actions, as well as critical information such as the type, location, and progress of the work object (Hentout, et al., 2019; Cheng, et al., 2024). This forms the foundation for autonomous collaborative work between humans and machines. Based on machine vision, the work process of HRC requires different characteristics of work objects

and operator actions to be addressed. On the one hand, YOLOv7 and transfer learning algorithms are used to recognize the work progress of the work objects. On the other hand, the fusion of LSTM and attention mechanisms is applied to real-time perception of the operator's actions. Information fusion is then used to support autonomous collaborative decision-making by the robot, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Perception Process of Human-Machine Collaborative Operation Status

Fusion of YOLOV7 and Transfer Learning

YOLO is a deep learning-based, single-stage object detection algorithm (Sirisha, et al., 2023). The core idea is to transform the object detection task into a regression problem, which can be solved through a single forward pass. The advantage of the YOLO algorithm lies in its speed and real-time performance. YOLOv7 is one of the most advanced algorithms in the YOLO series (Wang, et al., 2023). Considering the high demands for accuracy and efficiency in target detection for human-machine collaborative work, the YOLOv7 algorithm is used to recognize the state of collaborative work objects.

In intelligent manufacturing systems, key components often have similar image features. YOLOv7 models need to be quickly deployable when faced with new production tasks. However, during the training process, the initial results of the YOLOv7 model are often suboptimal, with large loss functions and significant variations in training results. Transfer

learning can accelerate convergence speed and reduce computational resources when training data is insufficient (Hua, et al., 2021). Therefore, transfer learning is applied to train YOLOv7, effectively utilizing the universal weights for recognizing similar features of components to improve training efficiency and accuracy, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. YOLOv7 Transfer Learning Training

Since the features extracted by the backbone network in the pre-trained model are general, the weights from the YOLOv7 pre-trained model based on the COCO dataset are used as the initial weights for training. Before training, the backbone network is frozen, and only the head network of the model is trained. The extracted features are used to perform classification tasks for key components (transfer learning process). By freezing the backbone network during training, not only is the training efficiency increased, but it also effectively prevents the destruction of feature extraction weights. During the freezing phase, only the head network is fine-tuned, keeping the feature extraction network stable, and requiring relatively less computational resources.

The loss function of this algorithm comprehensively considers both the coordinate loss of key component localization and the component classification loss function as $L_{task} = L_{cla} + L_{CIoU}$, where, L_{task} represents the loss function, L_{cla} is the component

recognition classification loss, and L_{CIoU} denotes the coordinate loss for key component localization. The calculation process for the component recognition classification loss is shown in equation (1), as:

$$L_{cla} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n y_i \log[\sigma(x_i)] + (1 - y_i) \quad (1)$$

here, n represents the number of component categories, and $\sigma(x_i)$ is the Sigmoid function. The y_i is a sign function. If the identified key component i belongs to the real category, its value is 1; otherwise, it is 0. The coordinate loss calculation for key component positioning adopts $CIoU$ loss to improve the stability of target box regression. The calculation process is shown in equation (2).

$$L_{CIoU} = 1 - IoU + \frac{\rho^2(b, b^{gt})}{c^2} + \alpha v \quad (2)$$

where, ρ is the diagonal distance between the minimum closure region of the predicted box and the real box. The b is the center point of the component recognition prediction box. b^{gt} is the center point of the real frame, α is the weight coefficient, and v is used to measure the consistency of aspect ratio.

LSTM and Attention Mechanism

In the process of human-machine collaborative work, efficient and accurate recognition of the operator's actions is equally important, as it provides real-time information about the operator's work state. This information serves as accurate and timely input for the robot's intelligent decision-making. Therefore, the LSTM algorithm, which excels in time-series data processing, is introduced, along with the attention mechanism to enhance the adaptability of the action recognition algorithm (Wang, et al., 2016; Xuan, & Deng, 2023). Specifically, machine vision is used to capture image data of the operator, extract key body information, convert it into time-series data, and input it into a neural network that fuses LSTM and attention mechanisms for action classification, thus achieving accurate recognition of the operator's actions, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Real Time Recognition of Operational Work Actions

Considering the complexity of the production environment, the MEDIAPIPE image

processing framework is introduced to extract key points of the operator's actions, minimizing the environmental interference during the action recognition process. Specifically, three major types of key points are extracted from the operator: hand key points, skeleton key points, and facial key points. Hand key points capture the details of actions during the operation, skeleton key points reflect the body information of the operator, and facial key points provide information on the operator's facial position and orientation. These key points provide critical information for the robot to assess the operator's work status.

By extracting these key points, the operator's action data can be continuously obtained. LSTM demonstrates its unique advantages when processing time-series information, such as operator actions. With the combined action of the activation function, input, output, and forget gates, LSTM can "remember" the historical information of the operator's actions (Khan, Afzal, & Lee, 2022). When processing the current action, it can capture the temporal dependencies in the sequence of the operator's actions, thus improving the efficiency and accuracy of action recognition. To enhance the model's learning ability and generalization, a multi-layer LSTM structure (see Figure 4) is used to process the time-series data of the operator's actions.

Human-Robot Smart Collaborative Based on LLM

Large language model is known for their excellent natural language understanding and logical reasoning abilities (Kim, Lee, & Mutlu, 2024; Jinnuo, et al., 2025). In this paper, we combine LLM with the hardware and software conditions of HRC work to build an intelligent decision-making system for robots capable of proactive collaboration. By fine-tuning a general-purpose LLM using domain-specific knowledge and logical chains, we adapt it to meet the inference needs of the intelligent manufacturing system. Furthermore, the information fusion obtained from the previous section is used to construct a framework for

human-machine autonomous collaborative decision-making, enhancing the autonomy and intelligence of human-machine collaborative tasks.

Fine-Tuning the LLM

Building a LLM from scratch for the intelligent manufacturing system domain requires large-scale data and computational resources, which can be time-consuming and costly. Given that general-purpose LLMs are trained on vast amounts of data, they contain rich semantic relationships and domain knowledge, making them an ideal foundation for customization and fine-tuning. By introducing logical chains, the LLM can break down complex problems into interconnected sub-problems and solve them sequentially, significantly improving the model's performance. Therefore, fine-tuning an LLM based on domain knowledge and logical chains not only reduces the training time and computational resources required but also allows the model to quickly adapt to new specific domains with limited data, providing strong support for rapid inference and decision-making in human-machine collaborative work.

This paper fine-tunes the general-purpose LLM in two stages. The training data consists of common human-machine collaboration rules, specific product manufacturing process knowledge, and information about typical scenarios. To better help the pre-trained model understand and fine-tune the data, the data is structured and transformed into a dialogue Q&A format for the overall fine-tuning of the general-purpose LLM. This allows the model to shift from a high-generalization model to a specialized LLM focused on human-machine collaboration scenarios in the intelligent manufacturing system. Since a general-purpose LLM cannot directly complete task operations from state perception to task instruction output, a logical reasoning chain is set up for human-machine task sequence inference to fine-tune the LLM. The fine-tuning process treats the model's information processing as a logical analysis sequence consisting of specific task scenario understanding, task state processing, and task instruction output, with each part being

independent. The input is a state prompt text for human-machine collaboration, and the output is task instructions for the collaborative robot. The reasoning process is divided into independent logical modules, allowing the LLM to first understand the scene information, then process the task state, and finally output the task instructions in the correct order. This greatly improves the LLM's ability to understand specific human-machine collaborative tasks and, under quick deployment and operation conditions, allows robots to more intelligently understand the operator's actions and actively complete complex collaborative tasks. The fine-tuning framework is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Fine Tuning Process of the Large Model

Additionally, output prompt templates are provided for the large model, ensuring that the fine-tuned LLM can output human-machine collaborative task instructions in a structured format, simplifying the encoding-decoding process and improving the efficiency of using the fine-tuned model.

HRC Decision-Making Framework

After fine-tuning the LLM, it needs to be integrated with the collaborative robot to form the intelligent decision-making brain for human-machine collaborative work, providing decision support for the autonomy of the collaboration, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Decision Framework Based on Fine Tuning LLM

First, the operator action information and work object state information are fused to create an input template that provides effective and trustworthy data support for human-machine collaborative decision-making. Then, the fine-tuned LLM analyzes and reasons the input structured information, forming the task progress and the next steps that need to be executed. This information is output in the form of prompt text. Finally, the output prompt text is decoded into control instructions for the collaborative robot to perform the next task. It is important to note that if any abnormal instructions occur during the task execution, the related task is immediately stopped to ensure the safety of the operator.

Applications

Enhanced manufacturing efficiency: By integrating machine vision and LLMs, the

proposed system enables robots to autonomously collaborate with human operators in real-time, allowing for more dynamic and efficient manufacturing processes. The system can optimize task allocation, increase production speed, and improve the overall quality of manufacturing tasks through real-time decision-making.

Flexible and adaptive workflows: The HRC framework allows operators and robots to adjust to changing task requirements. This adaptability is particularly beneficial for industries with rapidly changing product designs or production needs, such as automotive and electronics manufacturing.

Task complexity management: The system's ability to recognize and adapt to complex tasks enables robots to assist with more intricate, detail-oriented tasks, traditionally performed by human workers. This could include tasks such as precision assembly, quality inspection, or complex product design, where human skills are complemented by the robot's speed and strength.

Safety enhancement: The proposed system's real-time perception of both the work environment and the operator's actions significantly reduces the risk of workplace accidents. By allowing robots to identify unsafe conditions or human actions, the system can halt operations when abnormal instructions are detected, thus safeguarding human workers.

Customization and scalability: The fine-tuning of large language models to specific domains allows for the creation of highly specialized systems tailored to individual industries, facilitating the development of custom collaborative robots for various manufacturing sectors, from consumer electronics to heavy machinery.

Challenges in Implementing HRC

Data and computational resources: Developing and fine-tuning LLM and integrating machine vision systems require

significant computational resources and large-scale data. This can be a barrier for smaller manufacturing firms with limited access to such resources.

System integration: The integration of various technologies, including machine vision, deep learning, and LLMs, into existing manufacturing systems can be complex. Legacy systems may require significant modifications, and the coordination of these technologies within a cohesive framework poses significant engineering challenges.

Real-time performance: Real-time decision-making and dynamic task allocation require systems that can process data and respond rapidly. Ensuring that the entire human-robot collaboration system performs seamlessly under varying production conditions can be challenging, particularly when dealing with large volumes of data or complex task sequences.

Robot adaptability: While robots are effective in performing predefined tasks, adapting them to real-time changes in task dynamics or unforeseen obstacles remains a challenge. Ensuring that robots can autonomously handle unstructured environments and unforeseen issues, such as a malfunction in parts or unexpected operator movements, requires continuous improvement in AI and machine learning algorithms.

Cost of implementation: The initial investment for such advanced systems, especially in smaller manufacturing enterprises, can be substantial. The cost of hardware (such as deep cameras and sensors) and software (for deep learning models and fine-tuning) can pose a significant barrier to entry for many companies looking to adopt human-robot collaborative systems.

HRC and trust: Although human-robot collaboration promises greater efficiency, the relationship between robots and operators is still evolving. There are concerns related to human trust in robots, especially in high-stakes environments where safety is critical. Ensuring mutual trust and understanding between human operators and robots is essential for smooth collaboration.

Conclusion

Human-robot collaborative work in intelligent manufacturing systems is an important research focus in the industry 5.0 stage. To address the issues of autonomy and intelligence in human-machine collaborative processes, this paper proposes a method for human-robot smart collaborative work in intelligent manufacturing systems based on LLM and machine vision. Based on the analysis of HRC work scenarios in intelligent manufacturing systems, a human-robot smart collaborative framework is established. Machine vision and deep learning are integrated to achieve HRC work state perception. Under the empowerment of fine-tuned large models, intelligent decision-making for robot tasks during the collaborative process is carried out. The feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed method are verified through a practical case of reducer assembly.

Future research can further explore HRC decision-making methods based on domestic, lightweight large models, establishing embodied intelligence to improve the speed and accuracy of task decision responses. At the same time, target detection algorithms play a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of human-robot autonomous collaborative work, and it is necessary to further explore related innovative algorithms in future research. Additionally, current HRC work primarily focuses on systems consisting of a single robot and a single operator. Future research can expand to scenarios involving multiple operators and multiple robots performing collaborative work simultaneously, further breaking through corresponding theoretical methods, which holds significant scientific and practical value.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no Declaration of Interest.

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